

SUPER-RESOLUTION LUNAR ELEVATION AND JOINT REFLECTANCE RECONSTRUCTION: THE LUMOS FRAMEWORK AND THE DESIGN LOGIC OF THE ESA MÁNI MISSION. Iris Fernandes¹, Klaus Mosegaard¹ and Frédéric Schmidt², ¹Niels Bohr Institute, University of Copenhagen - Jagtvej 132, Copenhagen, Denmark, Corresponding author's email: iris@nbi.ku.dk, ²Université Paris-Saclay, CNRS, GEOPS - Rue du Belvédère Bâtiment 504, 91400 Orsay, France

Introduction: The lunar surface provides a detailed record of impact cratering, regolith evolution, and tectonic processes operating under low-gravity conditions. Although modern orbital cameras achieve sub-metre spatial resolution, existing topographic products remain limited by sparse laser altimetry sampling and photogrammetric or shape-from-shading reconstructions that rely on simplified reflectance assumptions and typically lack formal uncertainty quantification. This mismatch between image resolution and physically consistent elevation models restricts quantitative analysis of metre-scale morphology and limits confidence in slope and roughness estimates relevant to landing-site assessment.

To address these limitations, we developed LUMOS (LUminosity-constrained Multi-angular Observation Super-resolution) [1,2], a physics-informed Bayesian inversion framework [3] for the joint reconstruction of super-resolution digital elevation models (DEMs), spatially varying reflectance, and pixel-wise uncertainty estimates from multi-angular orbital imagery. LUMOS explicitly couples topography and photometry within a non-Lambertian reflectance model, allowing anisotropic regolith scattering and illumination/viewing geometry effects to be treated consistently. The Bayesian formulation

enables propagation of photometric and prior uncertainties into elevation and slope products, providing quantitative confidence estimates that are directly relevant for geological interpretation and mission de-risking.

Initial demonstrations using multi-angular LROC NAC observations show that LUMOS can recover metre-scale relief while preserving long-wavelength consistency with laser altimetry. However, performance is constrained primarily by the acquisition strategy of existing missions. LRO was designed to maximise surface coverage rather than angular diversity [4], resulting in geometries that are suboptimal for reflectance-constrained inversion.

Because reconstruction fidelity scales with angular sampling and spatial resolution, the development of LUMOS highlighted the need for a dedicated multi-angular imaging strategy. This recognition motivated the conception of the ESA Máni mission (Phase A), designed to acquire dense multi-angular lunar imagery optimised for physics-based surface reconstruction and uncertainty-aware terrain characterisation.

LUMOS Framework: LUMOS formulates surface reconstruction as a Bayesian inverse problem in which topography and reflectance are estimated jointly rather than sequentially (Figure 1). Observed

Figure 1- Super-resolution topographic reconstruction using LUMOS. (a) Low-resolution LOLA elevation prior. (b) LUMOS DEM at native NAC sampling (0.53 m/pixel). (c-d) Oblique perspectives of the reconstructed surface. The inversion preserves long-wavelength altimetric structure while recovering file-scale morphology from multi-angular radiometric constraints.

radiance is modeled using a non-Lambertian, kernel-driven bidirectional reflectance distribution function (BRDF), adopting the Ross–Thick Li–Sparse (RTLS) formulation to represent isotropic, volumetric, and geometric scattering components [5,6,7]. This formulation enables consistent treatment of anisotropic regolith scattering, shadowing, and illumination–viewing geometry effects that are not captured by Lambertian assumptions.

A low-resolution laser-altimetry digital elevation model (DEM), derived from LOLA measurements [1], is incorporated as a prior to constrain long-wavelength topography, while fine-scale structure is recovered from photometric variations across multiple illumination geometries. The coupled photometric-topographic system is solved using a Sylvester-equation-based formulation [8], avoiding empirical regularization tuning and enabling formal propagation of uncertainties from radiance and prior constraints into pixel-wise elevation and slope estimates. This uncertainty-aware formulation provides quantitative confidence measures directly relevant to geomorphological interpretation and terrain assessment.

In practice, reconstruction accuracy is governed primarily by angular sampling density and spatial resolution rather than by algorithmic constraints. Consequently, the attainable fidelity of reflectance-constrained inversion scales directly with observational geometry.

Demonstrating on Apollo 15 NAC Observations: We demonstrate LUMOS using multi-angular LROC NAC observations of the Apollo 15 landing site [4]. The reconstructed DEM achieves 0.53 m/pixel resolution, corresponding to native NAC sampling and representing more than two orders of magnitude increase in sampling density relative to the LOLA prior.

The LUMOS solution preserves long-wavelength consistency with altimetry while resolving subtle relief variations, small craters, and local undulations unresolved in laser-derived products. Oblique renderings illustrate surface continuity and the absence of illumination-correlated artefacts frequently observed in Lambertian shape-from-shading reconstructions.

Beyond elevation recovery, LUMOS retrieves

Figure 2 - Spatial distribution of the retrieved RTLS reflectance parameter (K_L). The detailed area (right) highlights rover tracks and the reflector, demonstrating fine-scale reflectance sensitivity independent of topographic structure.

spatially varying reflectance parameters and provides pixel-wise uncertainty maps for both elevation and slope (Figure 2). Uncertainty increases in shadowed regions and geometrically limited configurations, reflecting reduced angular constraints. Comparisons between Lambertian and RTLS-based solutions reveal systematic slope differences at the metre scale, with implications for geomorphological interpretation, regolith roughness estimation, and landing-site hazard analysis.

These results demonstrate both the capability of reflectance-constrained inversion and the extent to which performance is limited by the angular distribution of available LRO imagery, which was designed primarily to maximise surface coverage rather than geometric diversity.

Implications for Máni and Lunar Science: The sensitivity of LUMOS to angular sampling directly motivated the development of an observation strategy optimised for reflectance-constrained inversion. The ESA Máni mission (Phase A) is therefore designed to acquire dense multi-angular lunar imagery at ~ 0.17 – 0.2 m/pixel, providing the geometric diversity required for stable joint inversion of topography and reflectance.

Within this framework, LUMOS serves as the reconstruction architecture that translates multi-angular radiance measurements into physically consistent, uncertainty-aware surface models. Applied to Máni-resolution data, the framework is expected to enhance topographic fidelity, improve reflectance characterization, and enable quantitative assessment of metre-scale surface processes across candidate exploration sites.

By aligning observation strategy with inversion requirements, the Máni-LUMOS framework integrates geometry, reflectance modelling, and uncertainty quantification into a unified surface reconstruction approach, supporting both geological investigations, mission-level terrain risk assessment and science enabler.

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